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Impact Of School Community Relationship On Decision Making Of Public Secondary Schools In North Central Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the impact of school community relationship on decision making of public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. Seven research questions guided the study. Seven hypotheses were tested for the study. The researcher adopted descriptive survey research design. The population was 42,235 teachers from 6,601 public secondary schools in North Central, Nigeria. A sample of 845 respondents was selected using multi-stage sampling procedure. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire titled “School Community Relationship and Decision Making Questionnaire (SCRDMQ)”. It was a 35-item questionnaire on four point rating scale. The questionnaire was validated by three experts. Two experts in Educational Management Unit of Educational Foundations and one expert in the Department of Science and Mathematics Education, all in the Faculty of Education, Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. It was trial-tested on 40 teachers who were part of the population but not part of the sampled population. The result of the trial-test yielded a reliability coefficient value of 0.77. Data were analyzed using the descriptive statistics of Mean Score and Standard Deviations to answer the research questions while Chi-square was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that school community relationship has significant positive impact on decision making of public secondary schools in terms of problem identification, information availability and planning in North Central, Nigeria. It was concluded that school community relationship has significant positive impact on decision making of public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. The study therefore recommended among others the communities should make their resources, such as land, facilities, and expertise, available for school use while collaborating with school administrators to maximize their benefits. Such collaboration enhances the early identification of educational problems in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria by exposing infrastructural deficits, resource gaps, and learning challenges. These joint efforts promote the optimal use of resources, improve learning opportunities, and strengthen the relationship between schools and their host communities, thereby making it easier to detect and address problems affecting school effectiveness.

Keywords: school community relationship, decision making, problem identification, information availability and planning

INTRODUCTION

Management is concerned with acquiring utmost affluence with least efforts. Management is vital wherever group efforts are needed to be directed towards achievement of common goals (Nnadi, 2020). School management is significant in achieving the goals and objectives of education. Therefore,

management creates team work and team spirit in an organization by increasing a sound organizational structure that would lead to achievement of organizational objectives. It brings the human and material possessions together and motivates the people for the attainment of goals.

Management according to Ugwanyi (2015), is seen as a social process which is designed to ensure the cooperation, participation, intervention and involvement of people in the effective achievement of a given objective. Management is an indispensable and integral part of educational system in any nation. This is because the world sees education as a good investment for personal, social and overall national development. It also involves planning, organizing, directing, controlling, coordination and evaluating school activities to achieve the goals and objectives of secondary education (Adzongo, 2014). Management of secondary schools is the operation of secondary schools within the confines of their statutes in order to carry out their primary assignment of imparting knowledge to younger generation (Mamman, 2016).

Management of public secondary schools is therefore seen as the mobilization, coordination, harmonization and utilization of public secondary school resources for the achievement of public secondary school goals and objectives (Saiti & Saitis, 2015). Management of public secondary schools can also be seen as the judicious utilization of human, financial and material resources of public secondary schools towards the achievement of its goals (Akpakwu, 2012). Public secondary schools are the post primary institutions of learning established and managed by government, communities or religious bodies to provide learners with functional education in order to become useful for themselves, the society and for higher education (Saiti & Saitis, 2015).

In North Central Nigeria, there are many public secondary schools which seem to contribute in no small measure to the educational development in Nigeria through provision of manpower for the nation. These public secondary schools are managed by government who take major responsibility in the management of public educational institutions in Nigeria (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014). However, it is worthy to note that management of public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria in recent times, appears to face numerous challenges such as inadequate funding, school facilities, instructional materials, security challenges and many others. Anthony, Yara and Pev (2017) lament over some of the challenges facing management of secondary education in Nigeria noting that there is inadequate conducive classrooms, office accommodations in some schools while in some schools, books in the libraries are obsolete and laboratory equipment are in the state of disrepair. This situation in North Central Nigeria seems to make it difficult for the realization of the essence of establishing secondary schools.

The essence of establishing secondary schools is to prepare its recipients for useful living within the society and for higher education (FRN, 2014). This entails that ineffective management of public secondary schools may not achieve these cardinal objectives of secondary education in Nigeria. Public secondary schools as social institutions are established or situated within various host communities where students or learners are drawn from these communities. Ekwelum and Mbara (2017) state that a community is a group of people living in a geographical area who have identical culture, beliefs, values, traditions and are united with common interest. It is common interest that brings them together to share a territory. Therefore, a community is a social group, occupying a more or less defined geographical area and based on the feeling that people have for one another. Such feeling could accommodate the facility to identify a common sentiment, the ability to share a recognized way of life and the possibility of living wholly within such groups. This calls for a symbiotic and reciprocal relationship that would result into the promotion of educational development with its attendant individual and national growth (Bala, 2013).

School community relationship is a two-way symbiotic arrangement through which the school and the community cooperate with each other for the realization of the goals of the school and the community (Okwori & Ede, 2012). The success or failure of public secondary schools depends to a large extent on the level of relationship they maintain with their host communities. This makes it demanding on the school managers to identify the key areas of relationship between their schools and the host communities (Miller, 2011). Moreover, it may be seen that schools in pursuit of quality education, will require a lot of human, material and financial resources for building the capacity of the education system to be able to deliver high quality and relevant curriculum to learners of all ages. However, school administrators alone

cannot achieve this objective. It requires the cooperation of the school and the host community. This implies that, for effective management of public secondary schools, there is need for school community relationship.

School community relationship is a pre-requisite for achieving a meaningful educational objective of a school (Uzoechina, 2013). It is fundamental to note that school and the community need to work closely with each other to meet their mutual goals of provision and management of education as well as teaching, learning and enforcement of processes (Oniyangi, 2018). School community relationship may take different forms since it will be unrealistic to leave the management of secondary school education to government alone. This relationship is also at different rate and pace as well as the peculiarities of a given community, thus the strength of the school community relationship is determined by the characteristics of each community (Uzoechina, 2013).

School community relationship has a significant impact on problem identification in public secondary schools because effective collaboration between schools and host communities enables administrators to detect challenges early and respond appropriately. Through regular interaction with parents, community leaders, teachers, and other stakeholders, schools can easily identify problems such as poor academic performance, student indiscipline, insecurity, inadequate facilities, absenteeism, and teacher shortages before they become severe (Owan, 2019; Nwankwo & Nnorom, 2020). Community participation also enhances information sharing, monitoring, supervision, and collective problem solving, which improve administrative effectiveness and school management (Shittu, Idowu, & Adedapo, 2022; Eziamaka, Enwezor, Okafor, Obilor, Nwogbo, & Chukwu, 2025). Therefore, strong school community relationship promotes transparency, cooperation, and effective identification of educational problems in public secondary schools.

School community relationship has a significant impact on information availability in public secondary schools because effective collaboration between schools and host communities enhances the flow and exchange of important educational information. Through regular interaction with parents, teachers, community leaders, and other stakeholders, school administrators gain access to useful information concerning students' behaviour, academic progress, attendance, and social challenges, thereby improving school planning and administration (Nwankwo & Nnorom, 2020). This relationship also helps schools understand community expectations and educational needs.

School community relationship has a significant impact on planning in public secondary schools because effective collaboration between schools and host communities improves the formulation of educational plans and programmes. Through regular interaction with parents, community leaders, and stakeholders, school administrators obtain relevant information concerning school needs, students' welfare, infrastructural development, and academic priorities, which supports effective planning and policy implementation (Owan, 2019; Nwankwo & Nnorom, 2020). This cooperation helps schools align their objectives with community expectations and educational goals.

Recently, the current state of management of public secondary schools particularly in North Central, Nigeria appears to be discouraging as most schools appear to be managed in isolation or with little contribution of the host communities. The consequence may be poor quality secondary education. School and community are expected to thrive on a cordial relationship for sustenance and progress of both the school and the community. It is against this background that the study sought to investigate the impact of school community relationship on decision making of public secondary schools in North Central, Nigeria laying emphasis on problem identification, information availability and planning.

Statement of the Problem

Decision making is a vital component of educational management because it determines the effectiveness of policies, administration, and achievement of educational objectives in public secondary schools. Effective decision making in schools depends largely on proper problem identification, availability of accurate information, and strategic planning. In an ideal situation, public secondary schools are expected to maintain cordial relationships with their host communities in order to facilitate active participation of stakeholders in identifying school problems, sharing relevant information, and contributing to planning processes for effective school administration. School community relationship creates opportunities for

cooperation between school administrators, parents, community leaders, and other stakeholders in addressing educational challenges and improving management outcomes.

However, the current situation in many public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria appears discouraging as decision making processes seem to be characterized by inadequate collaboration between schools and host communities. It has been observed that many school administrators make decisions without adequate involvement of parents and community members who are important stakeholders in the educational system. This situation appears to affect effective problem identification in schools, as issues such as student indiscipline, poor academic performance, insecurity, inadequate facilities, truancy, and teacher shortages may not be identified early due to weak communication and poor interaction between schools and communities. Consequently, some school challenges continue to persist and negatively affect effective teaching and learning.

Furthermore, there appears to be inadequate availability and dissemination of information between schools and their host communities in North Central Nigeria. Many public secondary schools seem to experience poor communication channels, limited feedback mechanisms, and lack of transparency in sharing information relating to school policies, students' welfare, developmental projects, and administrative activities. This inadequate flow of information may hinder effective decision making, monitoring, supervision, and implementation of educational programmes. In some cases, community members may not have access to relevant information concerning school needs and activities, thereby reducing their willingness and ability to contribute meaningfully to school management and development. Planning in public secondary schools also appears to be affected by poor school community relationship. Effective planning requires collective participation, adequate information, and proper identification of school needs and priorities. However, it has been observed that many schools in North Central Nigeria seem to plan and implement programmes without adequate consultation with community stakeholders. This may result in poor prioritization of school needs, inadequate resource mobilization, weak implementation of projects, and unsustainable educational programmes. Lack of community participation in planning may also reduce accountability, transparency, and community support for school development initiatives.

Despite government efforts to improve management of public secondary schools through educational policies and reforms, the problem of ineffective decision making still persists in many schools in North Central Nigeria. The researcher observed that weak school community relationship may be responsible for ineffective problem identification, inadequate information availability, and poor planning in public secondary schools. These challenges appear to contribute to poor administrative effectiveness, weak educational outcomes, and slow development of public secondary schools in the region. It is against this background that the researcher deemed it necessary to investigate the impact of school community relationship on decision making in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria, with emphasis on problem identification, information availability, and planning.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the impact of school community relationship on decision making of public secondary schools in North Central, Nigeria. Specially, the study seeks to:

1. ascertain the impact of school community relationship on problem identification in public secondary schools.
2. find out the impact of school community relationship on information availability in public secondary schools.
3. examine the impact of school community relationship on Planning in public secondary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the impact of school community relationship on problem identification in public secondary schools?
2. What is the impact of school community relationship on information availability in public secondary schools?

3. What is the impact of school community relationship on Planning in public secondary schools?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. School community relationship has no significant impact on problem identification in public secondary schools.
2. School community relationship has no significant impact on information availability in public secondary schools.
3. School community relationship has no significant impact on involvement of community members in Planning in public secondary schools.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human relations theory of management was formulated by Elton Mayo in 1927. Elton Mayo formulated human relations theory through an experiment which he conducted to prove the importance of people for productivity – not machines. That is superiority of people over machines in the production process. The human relations theory of management believes that people desire to be part of a supportive team that facilitates development and growth. Therefore, if employees receive special attention and are encouraged to participate, they perceive that their work has significance and they are motivated they will be more productive, resulting in high quality work.

School community relationship encourages shared responsibility in addressing school challenges. When communities maintain close ties with schools, they provide useful feedback and local knowledge that help school administrators understand the root causes of problems affecting students and teachers. This cooperation strengthens trust, enhances communication, and enables schools to make informed decisions that improve teaching and learning outcomes. Effective partnership also increases community support for school programmes and interventions.

Good school community relationship promotes early intervention and conflict resolution in public secondary schools. Community members often assist schools in identifying social problems such as drug abuse, bullying, truancy, and violence among students. Their involvement helps schools implement preventive measures and maintain a peaceful learning environment. As a result, school administrators are better equipped to solve problems promptly and improve overall school effectiveness and students' academic development. Security ordinarily means safety, protection, to defend or freedom from damage or physical harm (Okam & Bozimo, 2014).

Furthermore, school community relationship promotes transparency and accountability in school management through effective dissemination of information. Community participation enables schools to communicate policies, programmes, academic activities, and developmental projects to parents and stakeholders in a timely manner. This improves trust, cooperation, and mutual understanding between schools and communities (Owan, 2019). Availability of accurate information also supports effective monitoring and evaluation of school activities.

Strong school community partnership strengthens feedback mechanisms and encourages timely sharing of information needed for effective teaching and learning. Community members often provide information relating to security, student welfare, and social issues affecting schools, which helps administrators make informed decisions and solve problems quickly (Shittu, Idowu, & Adedapo, 2022). Therefore, effective school community relationship improves communication, administrative efficiency, and overall management of public secondary schools.

School community relationship enhances resource mobilization and collective participation in planning school activities. Communities often contribute ideas, financial support, and local resources that assist schools in planning projects such as classroom construction, provision of instructional materials, and security improvement. Community involvement also promotes shared responsibility and strengthens strategic planning processes necessary for effective school management (Shittu, Idowu, & Adedapo, 2022). This creates a sense of ownership and commitment toward school development.

In addition, strong school community partnership promotes accountability, transparency, and sustainability in school planning. When communities are involved in planning processes, they help monitor the implementation of school programmes and ensure that decisions are properly executed. Their participation encourages trust, cooperation, and effective communication between schools and stakeholders. Therefore, effective school community relationship improves administrative efficiency, long term educational planning, and overall management of public secondary schools.

METHODS

Research Design

The research design adopted for the study was descriptive survey research design. According to Rick (2014), descriptive survey research design describes situations of what is being investigated as they exist in their natural setting. On the other hand, Bello and Ajayi (2010) opines that, this design is a method that is usually adopted when handling a large population especially on issue of the moment that involve systematic collection of data from population of study through the use of questionnaire. Descriptive survey design is chosen for the study because the study is descriptive in nature and it requires the use of questionnaire in the collection of data. It is considered the most appropriate for this study because it seeks to find out the factors that are associated with certain occurrences, practices, outcomes, conditions or types of behaviour by analysis of past events or of already existing conditions. The population for the study comprises 42,235 teachers from 6,601 public secondary schools in North Central, Nigeria (Federal and State Ministries of Education from North Central Nigeria, 2025) (Details in Appendix D, p.138). The population of the study was made up of teachers because they are better educated and informed to provide valid information on the variables of the study and their opinions were more reliable regarding school community relationship and management of public secondary schools. The sample size for the study comprised 845 or 2% of the 42,235 teachers and 132 or 2% of the 6,601 public secondary schools. This sample is in line with Osuala (2017) rule of Thumb which states that when the population is ten thousand 2 to 5 percent of the population will be considered representative. The multi-stage sampling was adopted for this study. A researcher's structured questionnaire was used for this study. The instrument was titled "School Community Relationship and Management Questionnaire (SCRMQ)". Due to the large geographical spread of respondents for the study, the researcher engaged five (5) research assistants who assisted in administering the questionnaire in the sampled schools. The data that obtained from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean scores and standard deviations to answer the research questions.

RESULTS

A total of 845 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents. However, 840 representing 99.4% copies of questionnaire were returned by the respondents while five representing 0.6% copies of questionnaire were recorded as attrition. The data obtained from the questionnaire were presented, analyzed and interpreted.

Research Question 1: *What is the impact of school community relationship on problem identification in public secondary schools?*

Table 1: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation Rating on impact of school community relationship on problem identification in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria

S/No	Item Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	Communities help schools to use its land for school farm	840	261	277	179	123	2.80	1.03	Agree
2	Communities allow schools to use its members as resources person for students' orientation	840	268	257	183	132	2.79	1.05	Agree
3	ICT centres in the community are used by students for practical on ICT skills acquisition	840	294	217	211	118	2.82	1.06	Agree
4	Community helps school with musical instrument to celebrate students' graduation	840	275	250	218	97	2.84	1.01	Agree
5	Community provides schools with vehicles to embark on field trips	840	288	241	206	105	2.85	1.03	Agree
Cluster Mean							2.82		Agree

Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2026

Table 1 shows mean ratings of 2.80, 2.79, 2.82, 2.84, 2.85 and cluster mean of 2.79 with a corresponding Standard Deviation ratings of 1.03, 1.05, 1.06, 1.01 and 1.03 respectively. The result indicated that the respondents agreed that communities help schools to use its land for school farm, communities allow schools to use its members as resources person for students' orientation, ICT centres in the community are used by students for practical on ICT skills acquisition, community helps school with musical instrument to celebrate students' graduation and community provides schools with vehicles to embark on field trips. The cluster mean value of 2.82 was above the mean score benchmark of 2.50. This shows positive impact of school community relationship has no significant impact on problem identification in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

Research Question 2: *What is the impact of school community relationship on information availability in public secondary schools?*

Table 2: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation Rating on impact of school community relationship on information availability in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria

S/No	Item Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	Provision of security materials like fire extinguisher enables schools to handle emergency situations	840	253	313	174	100	2.86	0.98	Agree
7	Communities bring security personnel to give security tips to school members for maintenance of safety	840	255	267	201	117	2.79	1.02	Agree
8	Communities through vigilante groups help in monitoring school activities to guide against loss of properties	840	245	216	229	150	2.66	1.08	Agree
9	Community through vigilante groups help schools in maintaining orderliness during sport competition	840	244	222	229	145	2.67	1.07	Agree
10	Communities helps in providing	840	232	245	225	138	2.68	1.04	Agree

security personnel to ensure safety of students during field trips

Cluster Mean **2.73** **Agree**

Source: Researcher’s Field Work, 2026

Table 2 shows mean ratings of 2.86, 2.79, 2.66, 2.67, 2.68 and cluster mean of 2.73 with a corresponding Standard Deviation ratings of 0.98, 1.02, 1.08, 1.07 and 1.04 respectively. The result indicated that the respondents agreed that provision of security materials like fire extinguisher enables schools to handle emergency situations, communities bring security personnel to give security tips to school members for maintenance of safety, communities through vigilante groups help in monitoring school activities to guide against loss of properties, community through vigilante groups help schools in maintaining orderliness during sport competition and communities helps in providing security personnel to ensure safety of students during field trips. The cluster mean value of 2.73 was above the mean score benchmark of 2.50. This shows positive impact of school community relationship has no significant impact on information availability in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

Research Question 3: *What is the impact of school community relationship on planning in public secondary schools?*

Table 3: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation Rating on impact of school community relationship on planning in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria

S/No	Item Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
11	Community members are always involved in decision making regarding school disciplinary policies	840	255	219	216	150	2.69	1.08	Agree
12	Community members are involved in decision making concerning recruitment of PTA teachers	840	260	222	179	179	2.67	1.12	Agree
13	Community members are involved in decision making concerning appointment of School Board of Governors members so as to contribute positively towards students’ academic progress	840	267	217	172	184	2.67	1.13	Agree
14	Community members are involved in decision making concerning provision of school facilities	840	238	235	175	192	2.62	1.12	Agree
15	Community members are involved in decision making concerning provision of instructional materials	840	257	243	162	178	2.69	1.11	Agree
Cluster Mean							2.67		Agree

Source: Researcher’s Field Work, 2026

Table 3 shows mean ratings of 2.69, 2.67, 2.67, 2.62, 2.69 and cluster mean of 2.67 with a corresponding Standard Deviation ratings of 1.08, 1.12, 1.13, 1.12 and 1.11 respectively. The result indicated that the respondents agreed that community members are always involved in decision making regarding school disciplinary policies, community members are involved in decision making concerning recruitment of PTA teachers, community members are involved in decision making concerning appointment of school board of governors members so as to contribute positively towards students’ academic progress, community members are involved in decision making concerning provision of school facilities and community members are involved in decision making concerning provision of

instructional materials. The cluster mean value of 2.67 was above the mean score benchmark of 2.50. This shows positive impact of school community relationship has no significant impact on planning in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: School community relationship has no significant impact on problem identification in public secondary schools.

Table 4

Chi-square Analysis of Impact of School Community Relationship on problem identification in Public Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria

Responses	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	P	df	χ^2	Decision
SA	277	210	0.000	3	74.381 ^a	Sig.
A	248	210				
D	200	210				
SD	115	210				
Total	840					

Source: Researcher’s Field Work, 2026

Table 5 shows Chi-square calculated value of 74.381^a at 3 degree of freedom; P=0.000 is less than 0.05. With this result, the null hypothesis which states that school community relationship has no significant impact on use of resources in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria was therefore, rejected. This means that school community relationship has positive significant impact on use of resources in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: School community relationship has no significant impact on information availability in public secondary schools.

Table 5. Chi-square Analysis of Impact of School Community Relationship on information availability in Public Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria

Responses	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	P	df	χ^2	Decision
SA	246	210	0.000	3	123.114 ^a	Sig.
A	252	210				
D	212	210				
SD	130	210				
Total	840					

Source: Researcher’s Field Work, 2026

Table 5 shows Chi-square calculated value of 123.114^a at 3 degree of freedom; P=0.000 is less than 0.05. With this result, the null hypothesis which states that school community relationship has no significant impact on provision of security services in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria was therefore, rejected. This means that school community relationship has positive significant impact on provision of security services in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3: School community relationship has no significant impact on planning in public secondary schools.

Table 6. Chi-square Analysis of Impact of School Community Relationship on planning in Public Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria

Responses	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	P	df	χ^2	Decision
SA	255	210	0.000	3	27.343 ^a	Sig.
A	227	210				
D	181	210				
SD	177	210				
Total	840					

Source: Researcher’s Field Work, 2026

Table 6 shows Chi-square calculated value of 27.343^a at 3 degree of freedom; P=0.000 is less than 0.05. With this result, the null hypothesis which states that school community relationship has no significant impact on decision making in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria was therefore, rejected. This means that school community relationship has positive significant impact on decision making in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section presents discussion of findings as follows:

The first finding of the study showed that School community relationship has no significant impact on problem identification in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. This finding shows that communities allow schools to use land for farming projects, provide resource persons for student orientation programs, make ICT centers available for practical skills training, lend musical instruments for graduation events, and provide vehicles for field trips. This finding aligned with the findings of Owan (2019) whose findings showed that parent-teachers' relationship, school-community use of resources, school-community communication and school-community collaboration are significantly related to secondary school system effectiveness respectively, in Calabar Municipal Area of Cross River State. The finding also agreed with the findings of Nakpodia (2011) whose findings revealed that community provision of physical facilities, instructional materials and use of resources have significant impact on management of public secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial District Nigeria. The researcher also agrees that school community relationship has positive significant impact on use of resources in public secondary schools because collaboration between schools and communities enhances the optimal use of available resources. For instance, communities might offer local facilities like halls or fields for school events, while schools may provide technical expertise or knowledge sharing. This synergy minimizes waste and maximizes resource utilization, benefiting both parties.

The second finding of the study showed that school community relationship has no significant impact on information availability in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. This finding signifies that communities supply security materials like fire extinguishers for emergency situations, engage security personnel to offer safety tips, and support schools with vigilante groups that monitor activities to prevent property loss. They also maintain order during sports events and ensure student safety during field trips by providing security personnel. This finding is in line with the findings of Etor, Etudor-Eyo and Godfrey (2020) whose findings showed that provision of security facilities and security personnel service delivery was significantly high in universities in Cross River State. The finding also agreed with the findings of Bala (2013) whose findings revealed that there was significant impact of community provision of security, participation in decision making, provision funds and provision of students' scholarship in secondary schools in Zamfara State. The researcher also agreed that school community relationship has positive significant impact on provision of security services in public secondary schools because school-community partnerships foster a sense of ownership and responsibility, leading to enhanced security measures. Community members often organize neighborhood watch groups or provide volunteers to safeguard school premises. This collaboration helps deter vandalism and theft, creating a secure environment conducive to learning.

The third finding of the study showed that school community relationship has no significant impact on planning in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. This finding indicated that community members actively participate in decisions about school disciplinary policies, recruitment of PTA teachers, appointments to school boards of governors, provision of school facilities, and procurement of instructional materials, contributing positively to students' academic progress. This finding is in line with the findings of Bakwai (2013) whose findings showed that there was significant impact of involvement in decision making, awarding students' scholarship, communication, collaboration and quality assurance in secondary schools in Zamfara State. The finding also agreed with the findings of Anthony, Yaro and Pev (2017) whose findings showed that Parents' Teachers' Associations, Old Students' Associations, school committees and school board of governors have significant influence on the management of secondary schools in terms of provision funding and decision making. The researcher also agreed that school

community relationship has positive significant impact on decision making in public secondary schools because communities involved in school decision-making processes bring diverse perspectives and local insights, ensuring policies and programs align with the community's needs. Their input fosters a sense of belonging and accountability, leading to decisions that are more inclusive and widely accepted.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it was established that school community relationship impact positively on management of public secondary schools in terms of problem identification, information availability and planning in North Central, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Communities should make their resources, such as land, facilities, and expertise, available for school use while collaborating with school administrators to maximize their benefits. Such collaboration enhances the early identification of educational problems in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria by exposing infrastructural deficits, resource gaps, and learning challenges. These joint efforts promote the optimal use of resources, improve learning opportunities, and strengthen the relationship between schools and their host communities, thereby making it easier to detect and address problems affecting school effectiveness.
2. Students should actively participate in community-led security initiatives by reporting safety concerns and adhering to safety protocols designed to protect the school environment. This participation improves the availability and flow of relevant information between schools and communities, especially concerning safety, discipline, and student behaviour. The collaboration between students and community security groups ensures timely sharing of information, reduces communication gaps, and promotes a safer learning environment. It also instills a culture of responsibility and vigilance among students in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.
3. Teachers in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria should work closely with community members in key decision-making processes such as establishing disciplinary measures, prioritizing resource allocation, and setting goals for school development. This inclusive approach improves planning by ensuring that school plans reflect both professional and community perspectives. It enables schools to align their policies with community values, leading to more realistic, acceptable, and effective educational plans. Ultimately, such collaboration strengthens trust, cooperation, and long-term development planning in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria.

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